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DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF THE PHILIPPINES' BUDGET PROCESS: ALIGNING IFMIS, BLOCKCHAIN AND LEGISLATION FOR SUSTAINABLE PFM REFORM

BY

JOHNRY A. CASTILLO

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CPBRD

HOUSE OF REPRESENTATIVES

BATASANG PAMBANSA, QUEZON CITY, METRO MANILA

TEL. NOS. 8931-60-32 OR 8931-93-92

Website: <http://cpbrd.congress.gov.ph>

ABSTRACT

This paper examines the Philippines' ongoing digital transformation in public financial management (PFM), focusing on the implementation of the Integrated Financial Management Information System (IFMIS), Budget and Treasury Management System (BTMS), and the potential integration of blockchain in the budget process within the context of current legislative initiatives. Using an analytical framework anchored on institutional readiness, systems integration, governance and accountability, and fiscal sustainability, the study assesses whether current technological ambitions align with the country's existing PFM capacity and reform trajectory.

Drawing from international experience, GovTech Maturity Index (GTMI) benchmarks, fiscal data, and comparative IFMIS and blockchain reforms, the paper finds that the Philippines continues to face structural constraints from fragmented systems, uneven interoperability, limited institutional capacity, and rising recurrent ICT costs associated with prolonged system development. While blockchain may enhance transparency, verification, and auditability, evidence indicates that it functions best as a complementary integrity layer rather than a substitute for core IFMIS functions. The paper argues that sustainable digital PFM reform requires a sequenced, system-driven, and technology-neutral approach that strengthens governance, completes IFMIS integration, and aligns innovation with institutional readiness and long-term fiscal sustainability.

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by Johnry A. Castillo*

INTRODUCTION

The Philippines is at a critical juncture where legislative momentum¹ is converging with large-scale digital transformation efforts. The implementation of the Public Financial Management (PFM) Reform Roadmap 2024–2028—anchored on the Budget and Treasury Management System (BTMS) and the broader Integrated Financial Management Information System (IFMIS)—coincides with legislative proposals that will institutionalize transparency, interoperability, and real-time access to public expenditure data.

Among the priority measures of the 20th Congress are the Citizen Access and Disclosure of Expenditures for National Accountability Act (CADENA) and the Progressive Budgeting for Better and Modernized Governance Act. The sustained public demand for greater transparency and accountability brings the proposed integration of blockchain technology into the national budgeting system or a blockchain-powered GAA², with features such as smart contract-enabled fund releases, decentralized validation, and real-time public expenditure tracking. While these initiatives are grounded in legitimate objectives, they raise critical policy concerns.

This paper argues that misalignment between technological ambition and institutional readiness poses significant risks to the effectiveness and sustainability of digital PFM reforms. Specifically, it contends that premature adoption of advanced technologies—particularly when embedded in technology-prescriptive legislation—may lead to (i) digitization of existing inefficiencies, (ii) increased fiscal exposure due to high-cost system investments, and (iii) reduced flexibility in adapting to future technological developments.

The paper contributes to the policy discussion by integrating institutional analysis, fiscal trends, and international benchmarking relative to the ongoing implementation of the IFMIS, BTMS and the potential integration of blockchain, within the context of current legislative initiatives. By benchmarking the Philippine experience against the GovTech Maturity Index

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¹ *Blockchain Technology for Government Efficiency Act (HB 4075), Philippine National Budget Blockchain Act (HBs 4380,4489, 4853,4935); Government Budget Blockchain Acts (HB 4611), Philippine Tokenization and Crypto Adoption Act of 2025 (HB 4792); Blockchain the Budget Act of 2025 (HB 5041); Digital Assets Act (SB 433); Blockchain the Budget Bill (SBN 1330).*

² *Department of Information and Communications Technology. (2026, January 15). PH makes history: First country in the world to put entire national budget on blockchain; Digital Bayaniban Chain ensures transparency, integrity, and accountability. <https://dict.gov.ph/news-and-updates/25385>.*

(GTMI), international and local practices, this paper assesses the readiness of the Philippine PFM system for advanced digital transformation.

Analytical Framework

This paper adopts a synthesized analytical framework as illustrated in *Figure 1* drawing from established literature on Financial Management Information Systems (FMIS) and digital PFM. In this paper, FMIS refers to the broader class of financial management information systems, of which IFMIS represents an integrated, government-wide implementation. Previous studies emphasize that the success of digital PFM reforms depends not only on technological deployment but also on institutional readiness, systems integration, governance structures, and fiscal sustainability (Dener et al., 2011; IMF, 2023; Cangiano et al., 2019). Building on these insights, the paper organizes these determinants into four interrelated dimensions, one of which (institutional readiness) operates as a cross-cutting enabler, to assess the Philippine context.

Source: Dener et al., 2011; IMF, 2023; Cangiano et al., 2019

The proposed framework aligns closely with the three core pillars of public expenditure management. These pillars—fiscal discipline, allocative efficiency, and operational efficiency—provide the conceptual anchor for the framework. One, fiscal sustainability reinforces fiscal discipline by ensuring that digital reforms remain affordable and do not generate unsustainable fiscal pressures. Two, systems integration supports allocative efficiency by enabling the consolidation of fiscal data across government, thereby improving evidence-based budget decisions. And three, governance and accountability underpin operational efficiency by ensuring that public resources are used as intended through effective controls and enforcement mechanisms. Institutional readiness serves as a cross-cutting enabler across all three pillars, determining the extent to which digital systems translate into actual improvements in PFM outcomes.

STATE OF DIGITAL PFM IN THE PHILIPPINES

Evolution of IFMIS and BTMS

The pursuit of an automated and integrated budget system in the Philippines is not new. Early efforts can be traced to 1998 with the development of the Budget Execution and Tracking (BEAT) system, supported by the World Bank (Diokno, 1999). It was an early attempt to automate budget execution (automates releases of obligational authorities and cash allocation) and accountability tracking (allotment, obligation, and disbursements) and served as a precursor to later IFMIS initiatives.

However, a more coordinated and system-wide reform agenda only emerged in 2009, when the Department of Budget and Management (DBM), Department of Finance (DOF), and Commission on Audit (COA) convened following the Public Expenditure and Financial Accountability (PEFA) assessment. The PEFA diagnostic highlighted fundamental weaknesses in the country's PFM system, particularly the fragmentation of financial information systems, weak cash management practices, and limited institutional capacity.

In response, the government initiated the development of the **Government Integrated Financial Management Information System (GIFMIS) in 2010**. Conceived as a whole-of-government platform, GIFMIS aimed to consolidate financial data across agencies into a unified, interoperable system capable of generating timely and comprehensive fiscal information.³ This initiative directly addressed structural deficiencies identified in the previous PEFA assessment, particularly the lack of integration across budgeting, accounting, and treasury functions.

Since then, **IFMIS has remained the cornerstone of successive PFM Reform Roadmaps**. As shown in *Table 1*, the evolution from the 2011–2015 to the 2024–2028 roadmap reflects a clear shift in reform orientation—from standardization and basic system development toward full digital transformation and interoperability. Central to this effort was the establishment of foundational standards such as the UACS, which enabled consistent classification, reporting, and consolidation of government financial data. This transition is closely linked to broader reforms in the budget regime, particularly the shift from an obligation-based system with multi-year validity to a cash-based system with a one-year horizon. The latter imposes stricter discipline on budget execution and necessitates more responsive, real-time financial management systems.

³ For clarity, GIFMIS refers to the original 2010 initiative, while IFMIS denotes the broader, evolving integrated PFM architecture under subsequent PFM reform roadmaps, with BTMS serving as its primary operational platform.

TABLE I
COMPARISON OF THE PFM REFORM ROADMAPS

Feature	2011–2015 Roadmap	2024–2028 Roadmap
Primary Goal	IFMIS, Standardization & Coding (UACS)	BTMS, Digital Transformation & Interoperability
Technology	Building basic IT foundations	AI-ready, Cloud-based, & Application Programming Interface (API)-integrated
Budget Regime	Obligation-based (2-year validity)	Cash-based (1-year validity)
Scope	National Government Agencies	National + LGU Integration

Source: PFM Reforms Roadmap (2011-2015 & 2024-2028)

Figure 2 presents typical features of an IFMIS⁴ which is often described as having two parts: “core” functions like accounting (financial) and reporting (information), and “non-core” functions such as budgeting, control, cash management, and disbursement. In practice, however, this distinction can be misleading because effective PFM requires all these functions to work together, not separately.

Despite these advances, the full realization of IFMIS has been constrained by a combination of institutional and technical challenges, including fragmented legacy systems, uneven agency capacity, and governance coordination issues. In response, the DBM adopted a more modular approach through the BTMS⁵, which focuses on integrating budget execution and cash management functions.

FIGURE 2
FEATURES OF A TYPICAL IFMIS

Source: Peterson (2006)

⁴ The IFMIS originally aims to (but not limited to): 1) standardize the processes across the budget cycle, defines and enforces user authorities, and centralizes reporting functionalities; 2) consolidate fiscal information across oversight and implementing agencies to support macroeconomic, monetary, and fiscal policy decision-making. This enables government-wide access to real-time information; 3) ensure comprehensive reporting on the actual expenditure of government agencies, and through the use of the Unified Accounts Code Structure (UACS), pave the way for better monitoring of programs and projects; and 4) enhance the cash management and the accounts receivable by facilitating revenue collection and management (DBM, 2014).

⁵ BTMS functions as the budget-execution layer within the evolving IFMIS architecture, which itself stems from the original GIFMIS blueprint.

Figure 3 presents the BTMS Functional Configuration that captures all financial transactions at source and in near real-time but only to cover national government agencies (excluding the GOCCs in the pilot phase). With this capability, transactions are mapped from the “cradle to the grave”, i.e., from purchase to payment. BTMS supported the existing disbursement frameworks, i.e., Modified Disbursement System (MDS) and Treasury Single Account (TSA). Thus, this enables the adoption of payment and cash management reforms. The BTMS Budget Utilization (BU) Module allows the recording of expenditure payments. After recording in the forms and books of original entries, the BTMS generated comprehensive financial reports at the consolidated government-wide (aggregated) and agency levels.⁶

The BTMS was piloted in 2018 with the following modules: Budget Management, Commitments Management/Budget Utilization, and Cash and Treasury Management.⁷ However, the Budget Management module and the Treasury Management modules, mainly designed for the oversight functions of the DBM and the BTr, respectively, were not fully rolled out.

Source: 2109/20 KSP Policy Consultation Report

In 2021, its rollout was suspended due to strategic reassessments of the overall IFMIS architecture (BTMS Advisory No.2021-08, 2021). Reform momentum resumed in 2022 with the relaunch of BTMS, signaling renewed commitment to completing the IFMIS agenda.

⁶ World Bank, IFMIS Capacity Building Program Virtual Workshop Report (2021)

⁷ <https://thedocs.worldbank.org/en/doc/3fjff7a44bd530a0413e23245ace2f03-0350012021/related/2021-IFMIS-CBP-Virtual-Workshop-Report-final.pdf>

While EO 29, s. 2023⁸ mandates the full implementation of IFMIS, current status went back to BTMS implementation which is no longer viewed as a standalone software project but as the primary vehicle for achieving a "modernized and harmonized" PFM system consistent with the PFM Reform Roadmap 2024-2028.

However, it must be noted that among the problems with BTMS in the past was the use of a commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) solution purchased in 2015 for the execution and accountability phases of the PFM cycle. This key limitation like many IFMIS designs were originally adapted from private sector systems, which means they do not always fully address government needs. Furthermore, the BTMS implementation reflects recurring challenges in system integration, leadership continuity, and implementation capacity among end-users (Magsino,2018; Castillo, 2022).

PHILIPPINES' GOVTECH MATURITY INDEX

The Philippines' progress in digital transformation can be more rigorously understood when assessed against the analytical framework of institutional readiness, systems integration, governance and accountability, and fiscal sustainability.

FIGURE 4
GovTECH Maturity Index, 2020-2025

Source of basic data: World Bank (2025)

⁸ *Strengthening the integration of public financial management information systems, streamlining processes thereof, and amending Executive Order No. 55 (S. 2011) for the purpose.*

Figure 4 presents the **GovTech Maturity Index (GTMI)**⁹ standing of the Philippines from 2020-2025, which provides a useful empirical benchmark to evaluate these dimensions. Based on a periodic assessment, typically within two-three years, the GTMI classifies the Philippines within Group B (Significant GovTech Maturity)—a classification it has maintained since 2020 (World Bank, 2025). This contrasts with regional peers such as Indonesia, Malaysia, and Thailand, which have transitioned from Group B to Group A (Extensive GovTech Maturity) over the same period.

From a quantitative perspective, Group B corresponds to a composite score range of approximately 0.50–0.74, indicating that while core digital systems and services are in place, **they remain incomplete, unevenly integrated, and insufficiently institutionalized**. In contrast, Group A economies—scoring 0.75 and above—demonstrate not only advanced digital infrastructure but also strong alignment between systems, institutions, and governance frameworks. The Philippines’ relative stagnation within Group B suggests that incremental improvements have not translated into systemic transformation.

Viewed through the paper’s analytical framework, the GTMI sub-indices reveal specific structural constraints:

- ❑ **Institutional Readiness (GovTech Enablers Index – GTEI)**. Institutional readiness remains uneven, particularly in the translation of policy initiatives into operational systems. While the Philippines has high maturity in adopting strategies and policies (i.e. National Digital Strategy, AI strategy roadmap, Green Tech), these have yet to be fully embedded within government operations or supported by a whole-of-government approach. The index assessed the country’s digital skills as still developing, highlighting the need to shift the focus from infrastructure to human capital, upskill the public sector, and foster a supportive ecosystem for GovTech entrepreneurs—areas where Singapore has already made significant progress. Compared to Indonesia and Thailand—which have invested heavily in digital ID systems, government cloud infrastructure, and innovation ecosystems—the Philippines’ digital initiatives often remain within individual agency silos rather than being integrated into a seamless national ecosystem.

- ❑ **Systems Integration (Core Government Systems Index – CGSI)**. The CGSI highlights persistent fragmentation in core government platforms. Although systems such as the BTMS represent important progress toward an IFMIS, interoperability across agencies remains limited. Legacy systems were developed at different points in

⁹ A World Bank composite indicator measuring digital government development across four dimensions: core government systems (CGSI), public service delivery (PSDI), citizen engagement (DCEI), and enabling environment (GTEI). Scores range from 0 to 1 and are grouped into four maturity levels, from minimal (Group D) to extensive (Group A). The index captures both the availability and integration of digital systems and is updated periodically to track progress over time (World Bank, 2025).

time by different vendors, and, using diverse technologies, resulting in incompatible backed technical foundations. These constrain the government's ability to produce real-time, consolidated fiscal data, undermining one of the primary objectives of digital PFM reform. In contrast, Group A countries have achieved higher levels of integration through unified data architectures and shared platforms.

- ❑ **Governance and Accountability (Digital Citizen Engagement Index – DCEI).** The Philippines continues to face challenges in institutionalizing transparency and citizen engagement mechanisms. While open data portals (Open Government Partnership) and feedback systems (8888 Citizens' Complaint Center) exist, their coverage and sustainability are inconsistent. Most public consultations still happen in "physical-first" town halls or fragmented social media pages rather than through a formal, secure Digital Participation Platform as defined by the World Bank. As a result, digital transparency remains episodic rather than systemic, limiting its impact on accountability. Higher-performing countries have embedded citizen-facing platforms within core systems, enabling continuous public oversight and data accessibility.
- ❑ **Fiscal Sustainability (Public Service Delivery Index – PSDI).** While the GTMI does not directly measure fiscal sustainability, the PSDI provides indirect insights into the efficiency of digital investments. Despite high internet penetration (approximately 84% of the population as of 2025)¹⁰, e-payment integration and high scores in portal maturity (e-gov PH App), the Philippines' PSDI is constrained by gaps in universal accessibility—"digital divide" persists in remote areas with low connectivity. This suggests that significant ICT expenditures (e.g. Philippines Digital Infrastructure Project) have not yet translated into integrated, cost-efficient service delivery, raising concerns about duplication of systems and suboptimal returns on investment (World Bank, 2025).

BLOCKCHAIN IN PFM: POTENTIAL AND LIMITATIONS

Blockchain in PFM has generated growing interest for its potential to enhance transparency and traceability in public spending, but its application also raises important limitations that must be assessed in light of institutional readiness, system integration, governance, and fiscal sustainability.

- ❑ **Institutional Readiness.** In the context of the GAA, it was highlighted that blockchain technology could function as an "immutable digital seal": once the budget is enacted and encoded into the system, any modification no matter how small—

¹⁰ Beltran, Bjorn Biel (2025). *Closing the distance to digital access*. *BusinessWorld*. <https://www.bworldonline.com/special-features/2025/04/09/665136/closing-the-distance-to-digital-access/>

would generate a permanent, traceable record that cannot be erased or altered. While there is strong push for government agencies such as the Department of Information Communications Technology (DICT), supported by the DBM and other agencies actively piloting use cases, a whole-of-government blockchain framework or standards has yet to be legislated. Limited technical capacity across line agencies and dependence on external vendors / pilot-based implementation are observed.

- ❑ **Systems Integration.** Since blockchain is effectively used for specific functions based on international and local benchmark studies (*Annex III*), it should operate as a layer on top, not a core backbone and as such, initial used cases remain siloed and are not yet integrated in IFMIS/BTMS architecture.
- ❑ **Governance and Accountability.** Blockchain has inherent limitations that constrain its applicability in PFM. First, it does not guarantee data quality. If inaccurate or manipulated data are entered into the system, blockchain simply preserves those inaccuracies permanently (OECD, 2018; Nguyen et al., 2023). Second, it does not enforce accountability. While it enhances transparency, it does not replace institutional oversight, audit functions, or enforcement mechanisms (OECD, 2020). Third, it introduces additional complexity and cost. Blockchain systems require specialized infrastructure, governance frameworks, and technical expertise. Notably, most government entities are not starting from scratch. They have decades-old "legacy" systems that don't speak the language of modern distributed ledgers such as the Blockchain which complicate the integration further.

According to the Department of Science and Technology (DOST), while blockchain technology can enforce technical rules, it cannot force people to be honest. If the personal gain for cheating is high enough, malicious users will still try to game the system. While open blockchains use rewards to encourage fair play, permissioned blockchains like those used in government rely heavily on a highly skilled, collaborative administrator to manage different agencies.

If legislation moves towards technology-specific provisions, it must clearly distinguish whether the blockchain is permissioned or permissionless, while recognizing that a fully private digital ledger controlled only by government nodes may remain vulnerable to internal collusion. According to the DOST-ASTI, there are two main types of blockchain, Permissionless (Public) and Permissioned (Private):

TABLE 2
TYPES OF BLOCKCHAIN BY ACCESSIBILITY

Particulars	Permissionless	Permissioned
Access and Participation	Open to anyone without prior approval	Restricted to authorized and vetted participants
Governance Structure	Decentralized and community-driven	Governed by a consortium or a single organization
Identity Management	Users operate through pseudonymous addresses	Participants are identifiable and typically subject to KYC requirements
Data visibility	Transactions are publicly visible by default	Data access is restricted and managed through role-based permissions
Cost Model	Transaction-based fees (e.g., gas fees)	No transaction fees; costs relate to infrastructure and system operations
Typical Use Cases	Public applications such as decentralized finance (DeFi), NFTs, and open digital assets	Inter-agency coordination, supply chain management, and financial consortia

Source: DOST-ASTI Presentation, 2026

Distinguishing between permissioned and permissionless blockchains is important because the choice has direct implications for governance, security, accountability, transparency, and legal risk—especially in public sector and policy application. Clear distinction helps policymakers match technology design to policy objectives, rather than adopting blockchain as a one size fits all solution.

FISCAL SUSTAINABILITY: COST OF DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION

Fiscal sustainability in digital public financial management is determined not only by the scale of ICT spending but by how digital investments accumulate over time and translate into enduring budgetary obligations. In the context of IFMIS reform, expenditures on hardware, software, connectivity, cloud services, and system maintenance are not standalone or discretionary items; they are foundational inputs to building an integrated, interoperable system capable of supporting the full budget cycle. This section examines the level, composition, and growth trajectory of ICT expenditures to assess whether current spending patterns are strengthening a coherent IFMIS architecture or generating long term fiscal pressures through fragmentation, duplication, and rising recurrent costs.

Table 3 shows ICT expenditures under the General Appropriations Act (GAA) has a cumulative allocation of P196.6 billion from 2022-2025, or an average of P49.2 billion annually. While this amount represents only about 1% of the total national budget, on average, ICT spending expanded by 71% during the period, driven primarily by hardware acquisition (41.3%), software subscriptions (16.7%), and connectivity services (13.4%)—collectively they account for over 71.3% of the total ICT expenditure.

ICT Equipment was the top expense category with P81.2 billion cumulative budget from 2022 to 2025. While it decreased in 2023, it recovered and peaked in 2025 which indicated

aggressive infrastructure build-up. Software subscription showed the highest growth pattern from P4.6 billion in 2022 to P12.5 billion in 2025 or a total of P32.8 billion over the four-year period.

TABLE 3
INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY (ICT) EXPENSES UNDER THE
2022-2025 GENERAL APPROPRIATIONS ACT, (AMOUNT IN MILLION PESOS)

ICT Expenditure Items	2022	2023	2024	2025	Ave. (22-25)	Ave.% Share
ICT Equipment	21,736.7	15,980.8	19,582.0	23,873.9	20,293.4	41.3%
ICT Software Subscription	4,596.6	7,000.9	8,672.4	12,501.9	8,193.0	16.7%
Internet Subscription Expenses	4,732.4	4,867.8	7,039.2	9,613.2	6,563.2	13.4%
Communications Equipment	2,484.3	1,065.4	3,745.9	3,024.3	2,580.0	5.2%
ICT Consultancy Services	1,586.2	25.4	5,062.6	1,665.3	2,084.9	4.2%
ICT Software	732.9	768.3	3,475.9	2,603.1	1,895.1	3.9%
ICT Office Supplies Expenses	1,099.5	932.0	2,139.4	2,627.7	1,699.6	3.5%
Computer Software	137.5	177.5	363.7	5,823.4	1,625.5	3.3%
ICT Equipment		880.3	1,195.8	1,831.5	976.9	2.0%
Rents – ICT Machinery and Equipment	383.9	715.3	1,043.7	1,754.7	974.4	2.0%
ICT Training Expenses	759.6	361.1	643.0	703.3	616.7	1.3%
Cable, Satellite, Telegraph and Radio Expenses	510.9	482.8	894.0	535.6	605.8	1.2%
Communications Networks	677.5	935.7	314.8	451.6	594.9	1.2%
Cloud Computing Service	67.1	54.8	88.8	420.7	157.8	0.3%
Website Maintenance	8.6	402.1	60.9	24.7	124.1	0.3%
Data Center Service		280.3	29.4	73.5	95.8	0.2%
ICT Research, Exploration and Development Expenses	4.1	40.3	17.2	132.7	48.6	0.1%
Communications Equipment	57.0				14.2	0.0%
ICT Generation, Transmission and Distribution Expenses			30.1		7.5	0.0%
ICT Machinery and Equipment	4.0	3.6	3.8	6.0	4.3	0.0%
Grand Total	39,578.9	34,974.4	54,402.5	67,666.9	49,155.7	100%

Source: General Appropriations Act, 2022-2025

FIGURE 5
ICT RELATED EXPENDITURE ITEMS, 2022-2025
(AMOUNT IN MILLION PESOS)

Source: General Appropriations Act, 2022-2025

The third highest allocation pertains to Internet Subscription with P26.3 billion, an increase from P4.7 billion to P9.6 billion showing steady and accelerating growth in internet use of

all government agencies. This combination likely suggests that the national government is moving from asset ownership to digital service ecosystems with a shift toward subscription-based services and connectivity scaling (*Figure 5*).

FY 2026 ICT BUDGET BY DEPARTMENT

While aggregate ICT expenditures illustrate the magnitude of digital transformation costs, fiscal sustainability ultimately depends on how these resources are allocated across institutions responsible for designing, implementing, and governing PFM reforms. The FY 2026 ICT budget by department provides an institutional lens on sustainability, revealing whether digital investments are being concentrated in agencies that anchor IFMIS integration and oversight, or dispersed across line agencies in ways that risk entrenching fragmented systems with recurring fiscal obligations.

While this year's budget saw a marginal increase of 0.7% (from P67.7 billion in 2025 to P68.5 billion in 2026), it reflects a substantial 73.0% growth from P39.6 billion in 2022. *Table 4* presents ICT related expenditures by department for 2026. Overall, the GAA level of ICT expenditure was reduced by P18.8 billion from the National Expenditure Program (NEP). The department's ICT budgets account for 99.1% of the national government's total ICT allocation, while the Budgetary Support to Government Corporations (BSGC) under the Special Purpose Fund accounts for only 0.9%.

TABLE 4
FY 2026 ICT RELATED EXPENDITURES BY DEPARTMENT
(AMOUNT IN MILLION PESOS)

DEPARTMENT	NEP	GAA	Inc/Dec	% Share
DICT	15,193.65	13,334.73	(1,858.93)	19.5%
DepEd	16,451.68	10,703.14	(5,748.54)	15.6%
JUDICIARY	6,312.31	6,962.31	650.00	10.2%
DOF	5,622.76	5,722.76	100.00	8.4%
DILG	5,762.09	5,682.38	(79.71)	8.3%
DOJ	5,051.01	3,793.05	(1,257.96)	5.5%
DOTr	2,803.31	2,545.37	(257.94)	3.7%
OEOs	2,292.44	2,430.16	137.73	3.5%
DND	2,091.73	2,091.73	0.00	3.1%
DENR	1,930.07	1,511.53	(418.53)	2.2%
DFA	1,964.87	1,308.95	(655.91)	1.9%
DBM	1,212.56	1,212.56	0.00	1.8%
SUCs	1,168.80	1,170.31	1.51	1.7%
DOH	2,464.50	1,065.48	(1,399.03)	1.6%
DOLE	1,003.24	932.91	(70.33)	1.4%
DEPDev	1,114.86	760.45	(354.41)	1.1%

DTI	822.19	695.87	(126.33)	1.0%
DOE	686.42	688.37	1.95	1.0%
CSC	1,973.11	679.48	(1,293.63)	1.0%
DOST	615.81	615.81	0.00	0.9%
DA	653.52	583.79	(69.73)	0.9%
COMELEC	574.14	574.14	0.00	0.8%
OMBUDSMAN	568.74	568.74	0.00	0.8%
DSWD	5,387.60	554.19	(4,833.41)	0.8%
DAR	437.00	437.00	0.00	0.6%
DMW	415.27	358.72	(56.56)	0.5%
DOT	332.46	332.46	0.00	0.5%
CHR	147.32	147.32	0.00	0.2%
PCO	134.42	134.42	0.00	0.2%
DHSUD	117.96	79.86	(38.10)	0.1%
CONGRESS	68.09	68.09	0.00	0.1%
OVP	59.32	59.32	0.00	0.1%
COA	54.93	54.93	0.00	0.1%
OP	39.90	39.90	0.00	0.1%
DPWH	1,795.32	14.92	(1,780.39)	0.0%
Total, Department	87,323.40	67,915.15	(19,408.24)	99.1%
BSGC	8.49	603.49	595.00	0.9%
ALGU	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.0%
Total, SPFs	8.49	603.49	595.00	0.9%
GRAND TOTAL	87,331.89	68,518.65	(18,813.24)	100%

Source: National Expenditure Program, General Appropriations Act (2026)

Among all departments, the DICT holds the largest share at 19.5% (or P13.3 billion in the GAA), albeit lower by P1.9 billion compared to the NEP. This is followed by DepEd at 15.6% (P10.7 billion)—despite the highest budget cut of P5.7 billion; the Judiciary at 10.2% (P7.0 billion), the DOF and the DILG, which accounted for 8.4% (P5.7 billion) and 8.3% (P5.7 billion) respectively. Looking at core PFM institutions or what Andrews (2014) classifies as concentrated agents (DBM, DOF, DepDev, COA, OP), institutions that should standardize, integrate, and govern systems, have a total budget allocation of only P7.8 billion or 11.5% of the total FY 2026 GAA ICT expenditures, which is relatively small and structurally inverted if the goal is integrated PFM and digital government.

DBM PFM REFORM PROGRAM: FISCAL IMPLICATIONS OF IFMIS AND BTMS

The fiscal consequences of IFMIS and BTMS implementation are clearly reflected in the DBM's PFM Reform Program, where multiyear appropriations, obligations, and disbursements capture both the cost of system development and the government's capacity to translate spending into operational outcomes. From a fiscal sustainability perspective, the key issue

is not simply under execution, but the consistency of financial commitments amid shifting system designs—resulting in sunk costs, contractual rigidity, and rising recurrent expenditures that constrain future fiscal space.

The funding for IFMIS/BTMS is usually lodged under the PFM program of the DBM. The PFM program includes critical digital transformation projects such as the Project Digital Information for Monitoring and Evaluation (DIME), managed services for the portal integration of DBM, subscription to low-code front end automation, dark fiber, application programming interface (API) and the Product Support Maintenance and enhancement for the BTMS, among others.

Table 5 presents the PFM Program's budget utilization from 2020 to 2025, revealing persistently low obligation and disbursement rates closely associated with the development trajectory of the BTMS. Beginning in 2019, the government entered into contractual arrangements with Innove and FreeBalance,¹¹ effectively committing substantial resources to BTMS maintenance. However, from 2020 to 2022, both obligation and disbursement rates declined sharply, coinciding with the indefinite suspension of BTMS and strategic shifts in the IFMIS design under the PFM Reform Roadmap. IFMIS was later formally strengthened and reaffirmed through Executive Order No. 29 (June 1, 2023), which prioritizes integrated, end to end financial management systems across government.

TABLE 5
PUBLIC FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT (PFM) PROGRAM BUDGET UTILIZATION, 2020-2025,
(AMOUNT IN MILLION PESOS)

Years	Appropriations	Obligations	Disbursements	Obligation Rate (%) ^{a/}	Disbursement Rate (%) ^{b/}
2020	414.9	252.0	249.0	60.7	60.0
2021	161.3	0.4	0.2	0.2	0.1
2022	308.8	0.5	0.0	0.2	0.0
2023	671.1	590.8	378.8	88.0	56.4
2024	448.9	294.4	89.9	65.6	20.0
2025	660.7	457.6	191.0	69.3	28.9

^{a/} Obligation rate – ratio of obligations to appropriations

^{b/} Disbursement rate – ratio of disbursements to appropriations

Source: SAAODB 2020-2025 (FAR No. 1)

Despite this suspension, the government continued to incur significant financial obligations for system maintenance, reflecting contractual rigidity and persistence of sunk costs. This pattern continued in 2024, when a P326.7 million contract was directly awarded to FreeBalance (Philippines), Inc. covering the 2024–2027 period (equivalent to P108.9 million annually)¹².

¹¹ *Inquirer.net*. (2019, January 16). DBM launches new govt financial management system for better transparency, accountability. <https://business.inquirer.net/263765/dbm-launches-new-govt-financial-management-system-for-better-transparency-accountability>

¹² DBM Notice of Award (NOA) and Contract Agreement (Contract No. 2024-53) dated December 4, 2024.

While obligation rates have improved, disbursement performance remains weak, with actual payments for delivered goods and services ranging only from 20.0% to 28.9% in 2024–2025. This divergence between obligations and disbursements suggests underlying inefficiencies in implementation, the incurrence of sunk costs amid absorptive capacity constraints, or misalignment between system development and operational readiness.

The cost profile of IFMIS in the Philippines reflects a long-term fiscal commitment rather than a one-time capital investment. Beyond initial development, IFMIS requires sustained funding for system upgrades, interoperability, cybersecurity, and ongoing maintenance. The indicative budget for IFMIS was estimated at P2.1 billion (approximately USD40.4 million). However, cumulative implementation costs had already reached about USD32 million (P1.5 billion) as early as 2020. These expenditures include BTMS-related rollout costs, change management, infrastructure upgrades, and other overhead requirements (KPFIS, 2021).

Subsequent financial commitments further underscore the recurring nature of these costs. These include P326.73 million for BTMS software and maintenance, a World Bank-supported IFMIS modernization loan of approximately USD400 million, and a cloud infrastructure subscription with support and maintenance for BTMS valued at P223.0 million in 2025 (DBM, 2026). Taken together, these figures highlight that digital PFM reforms entail continuous and escalating fiscal obligations, particularly as systems evolve toward greater integration and functionality.

This cost trajectory is consistent with global experience. Technological PFM reforms have proven to be resource-intensive and financially demanding, with development partners investing over USD20 billion in such initiatives worldwide (Fritz et al., 2017). IFMIS projects alone accounted for approximately USD6.5 billion across 168 projects in 86 countries as of January 2026 (World Bank, 2026).¹³ These figures reinforce a critical policy insight: while IFMIS can deliver substantial gains in transparency and fiscal control, their implementation requires careful sequencing, strong governance, and sustained fiscal discipline to ensure value for money.

FISCAL SUSTAINABILITY RISKS OF INTEGRATING BLOCKCHAIN THE BUDGET PROCESS

Proposals to integrate blockchain into the budget process must be assessed against the existing cost structure and fiscal commitments of digital PFM reform. Although initial implementation may be supported through private sector grants and presented as cost neutral, blockchain systems introduce long term fiscal obligations related to maintenance, upgrades, cybersecurity,

¹³ 143 completed + 25 active + 2 pipeline in 86 countries.

governance, and system interoperability. From a fiscal sustainability standpoint, the central risk is that blockchain adoption—if mandated or deployed prematurely—may create parallel digital infrastructures that duplicate IFMIS functions, increase vendor dependency, and compound recurring costs without proportionate gains in PFM performance.

The initial rollout of the blockchain system for the 2026 GAA was reported to have no cost to the national government¹⁴. While blockchain system is initially provided as grant, it nonetheless entails costs related to maintenance, upgrades, cybersecurity safeguards, and interoperability adjustments. This raises the risk of possible vendor lock-in, whereby the government may become dependent on the granted platform and compelled to continuously fund its upkeep, mirroring the experience with the BTMS since 2019. Moreover, if the CADENA Act (Senate Bill No. 1506) or the counterpart consolidated blockchain bills in the House is signed into law, the blockchain infrastructure will receive an official budgetary allocation of P500.0 million annual allocation.¹⁵

Various studies (Dener et al., 2011; World Bank, 2016; OECD, 2020; Godwin, 2024) highlighted that a technology-prescriptive approach explicitly mandating specific technology such as blockchain in the proposed legislations carries several policy, fiscal, governance and implementation risks, as follows:

- ❑ **Cost Duplication and Inefficiency.** Mandating blockchain before achieving full IFMIS integration may result in parallel systems performing overlapping functions (e.g., tracking, verification, reporting), leading to inefficient allocation of scarce fiscal resources.
- ❑ **Vendor Lock-in and Reduced Competition.** Technology-prescriptive legislation may constrain procurement options by favoring specific architectures or vendors, thereby reducing competitive pressure and increasing lifecycle costs.
- ❑ **High Sunk Costs and Reduced Adaptability.** Once implemented, blockchain-based systems are costly to modify or replace. This creates path dependency, limiting the government's ability to adapt to more efficient or appropriate technologies in the future. The costs are already there even if the product is being developed.
- ❑ **Risks of Rapid Technological Obsolescence.** Technologies evolve much faster than legislation. Hard-coding a specific technology such as blockchain risks locking the government systems into tools that may become outdated, inefficient, or inferior within a few years. The proposed CADENA Law may mandate the continued use of said technology even when better, cheaper, or more secure alternatives emerge.

¹⁴ *The infrastructure will be supported by a private-sector grant from BayaniChain, a local blockchain entity, developed through a private sector grant from the blockchain firm Polygon, and estimated to be valued at between USD5 million and USD10 million (BitPinas, 2026; Ayeng, 2026)*

¹⁵ *Per provisions of HBs 6909, 5041, 4935, 4853, 4489, and 4380.*

- ❑ **Misalignment with operational and institutional readiness.** Mandating the adoption of a specific technology does not inherently ensure adequate technical skills within government, effective process reengineering, sound data governance, or sufficient absorptive capacity at the agency and LGU levels. Such misalignment may result in low system utilization, symbolic or compliance-driven adoption, and non-integration with core financial management processes. As observed in earlier reform initiatives, this could lead to rising obligations without corresponding improvements in disbursements or tangible operational outcomes.

INSIGHTS FROM INTERNATIONAL AND PHILIPPINES EXPERIENCE

International and national experiences point to a consistent pattern in digital public financial management (PFM) reform: sustainable improvements in fiscal discipline, transparency, and reporting are achieved through **sequenced, system driven reforms**, rather than through the early adoption of advanced or emerging technologies. Across ASEAN, Africa, and digitally advanced governments, reforms that delivered durable outcomes prioritized the consolidation of **IFMIS** as the core fiscal backbone, supported by sustained institutional investment and governance reforms (*Table 6*).

TABLE 6
INTERNATIONAL EXPERIENCE IN DIGITAL PFM REFORM: SYSTEM ROLE AND TIME TO MATURITY

Region / Country	Core PFM System	Average Time to Maturity	Role of Blockchain
Indonesia	SPAN (IFMIS)	10–15 years	None (no core use)
Thailand	GFMIS	10–15 years	None (no core use)
Ghana	GIFMIS	10+ years	None
Estonia	IFMIS based e Gov	Mature	Integrity layer only
Philippines	GIFMIS / BTMS	Ongoing (15+ years)	Verification / authentication

Source: Adapted from Dener et al. (2011); Hashim (2014); World Bank (IEG, 2014); World Bank country reports on Indonesia SPAN and Vietnam TABMIS; and related IFMIS case studies.

ASEAN experience illustrates both the potential benefits and the fiscal demands of such an approach. Countries such as Indonesia and Thailand achieved significant gains in cash management, treasury integration, and fiscal reporting through SPAN and GFMIS, respectively. However, these outcomes emerged only after long implementation horizons—typically exceeding a decade—and substantial recurrent expenditures for system maintenance, upgrades, and capacity building. Importantly, these reforms focused on strengthening interoperability, standardizing processes, and embedding systems institutionally; emerging technologies such as blockchain were not adopted as core PFM platforms (*Annex I*).

African IFMIS reforms reinforce these lessons by highlighting the fiscal risks associated with weak execution and institutional misalignment. Experiences from Tanzania, Ghana, and

Kenya show that when implementation outpaced coordination and absorptive capacity, digital reforms resulted in partial rollouts, rising maintenance costs, and vendor dependence, with limited improvements in PFM outcomes. These cases underscore a critical fiscal sustainability insight: **digital reforms continue to generate costs even when benefits fail to materialize**, leading to sunk investments and reduced budget flexibility rather than efficiency gains (*Annex II*).

Advanced digital governments provide additional perspective on the appropriate role of frontier technologies. In Estonia, Georgia, and Brazil, blockchain has been applied in narrowly defined functions—such as data integrity, record verification, and conditional fund tracking—operating on top of mature digital government and financial management systems. Philippine experience mirrors this pattern, with blockchain solutions largely confined to document authentication and credential verification. Across all cases, blockchain has not replaced IFMIS or treasury systems; instead, it functions as a complementary layer whose value depends on the strength of underlying institutions and system integration.

Taken together, international and Philippine experience demonstrate that **digital PFM reform is most effective and fiscally sustainable when anchored on integrated core systems, disciplined sequencing, and strong governance**, rather than on technology driven experimentation.

STRATEGIC IMPLICATIONS FOR SUSTAINABLE PFM REFORMS

Several core lessons emerge from international and national practice that are directly relevant to fiscal sustainability and PFM reform in the Philippines. First, strong core systems remain the indispensable foundation of digital PFM. No country has successfully replaced IFMIS with blockchain or other frontier technologies; rather, IFMIS continues to serve as the central mechanism for fiscal control, reporting, and accountability. Attempts to bypass or substitute these systems have tended to increase, rather than reduce, fiscal and operational risk.

Second, emerging technologies have consistently proven to be **complementary rather than transformational** in PFM. Where blockchain has added value, it has done so in narrowly scoped applications—such as verification, audit trails, and conditional transactions—layered onto existing systems. This suggests that the fiscal returns to blockchain depend not on its scale of deployment, but on careful alignment with specific governance or integrity objectives.

Third, sequencing has been a decisive factor in managing fiscal risk. Countries that adopted incremental, modular approaches were better able to adapt systems to institutional capacity, manage recurrent costs, and avoid large sunk investments. By contrast, reforms that expanded system scope prematurely often faced cost escalation, duplication, and weak utilization, undermining value for money.

Fourth, institutional readiness has consistently outweighed technological sophistication as a determinant of success. Governance arrangements, inter agency coordination, and human capital shaped whether digital investments translated into improved PFM outcomes. Weak execution did not halt spending but instead entrenched long term maintenance obligations and contractual rigidity, reducing fiscal flexibility.

Finally, international evidence cautions against technology prescriptive reform paths. Mandating specific technologies before consolidating IFMIS integration has been associated with parallel systems, vendor lock in, and rising recurrent costs. From a fiscal sustainability perspective, reforms are most resilient when legislation remains outcome focused and technology neutral, allowing systems to evolve in response to institutional maturity and cost considerations.

A CURSORY REVIEW OF IFMIS AND BLOCKCHAIN LEGISLATIVE PROPOSALS

Building on international lessons and the state of digital PFM in the Philippines, this section assesses pending legislative proposals on blockchain and IFMIS in terms of their alignment with system readiness, institutional capacity, and global reform patterns.

TABLE 7
ASSESSMENT OF THE PROPOSED LEGISLATION ON IFMIS

Bill	Policy Approach	Scope of Reform	Alignment with IFMIS & GTMI	Fiscal & Implementation Risk
SBN 115 (Sec.50) / 1358 (Sec.47): Budget Modernization Act	Institutional + System modernization (structured reform) with embedded performance reforms	Strengthening budgeting processes, integration, and digitalization and fiscal controls	High – aligns with IFMIS development and GTMI gaps (CGSI, PSDI)	Moderate – depends on execution capacity
HB 11, 1788, 1921, 3194, 5156, 6128 (Budget Modernization / Progressive Budgeting Bills)	Structural + performance oriented reforms	Budget process improvements, performance-based and digital enhancements	High – supports system integration and governance improvements	Moderate – coordination and institutional capacity required
SBN 1489(Sec.49): Progressive Budgeting Act	Performance-oriented budgeting reform	Links budgeting to outcomes and efficiency, strengthening results-based budgeting	Moderate–High – strengthens governance and accountability	Moderate – requires strong data systems (IFMIS dependency)
SBN 1921: Philippine Budgeting Code	Comprehensive codification and structural budget reform	Institutionalizes budget processes, clarifies roles, and fiscal discipline, transparency and accountability mechanisms	Moderate – supports governance but less explicit on digital integration	Moderate–High – complexity of implementation

Source: Author’s compilation based on Bills uploaded in senate.gov.ph and congress.gov.ph

The proposed IFMIS-related bills—including the Budget Modernization Act and Progressive Budgeting Act and the most recent Philippine Budgeting Code—represent a more institutionally grounded approach to PFM reform compared to blockchain-focused proposals. These

measures emphasize improvements in budgeting processes, system integration, and fiscal governance, aligning closely with international evidence on successful IFMIS implementation (*Table 7*).

Unlike technology-prescriptive legislation, these bills adopt a largely technology-neutral orientation, allowing digital systems to evolve in line with institutional capacity and system readiness. This is consistent with global experience, where reforms in countries such as Indonesia and Thailand prioritized the development of integrated financial management systems before introducing more advanced digital tools.

The proposed Budget Modernization Act and Progressive Budgeting Bills, explicitly institutionalize an IFMIS, whereas the Philippine Budgeting Code merely mentions digitalization towards IFMIS as a governing principle. Meanwhile, the proposed blockchain legislation introduces a critical policy tension between technology neutrality and technology prescription, unless these measures are not further refined or amended.

The principle of technology neutrality holds that legislation should articulate policy objectives rather than prescribe specific technological solutions, thereby preserving flexibility as technologies evolve. Although some scholars argue that limited and carefully designed departures from strict neutrality may enhance regulatory clarity (Ojanen, 2025), the broader literature cautions against both extremes. Technology-neutral frameworks risk becoming overly abstract and difficult to operationalize or enforce (Puhakainen & Väyrynen, 2021), whereas technology-prescriptive approaches may lead to premature lock-in, reduced adaptability, and inefficient resource allocation of public resources (Greenberg, 2016).

Table 8 presents the initial assessment of proposed legislations on blockchain. In the context of PFM, mandating blockchain is particularly problematic. It risks committing government to a specific technological architecture before foundational systems—such as IFMIS—are fully integrated. Moreover, blockchain addresses a narrow set of issues (data integrity and traceability) while leaving core challenges—such as data quality, institutional coordination, and enforcement—largely unresolved. As a result, its legislative adoption may misalign solutions with system constraints and divert attention from more critical reforms.

TABLE 8
ASSESSMENT OF THE PROPOSED LEGISLATION ON BLOCKCHAIN

Bill	Policy Approach	Scope of Reform	Alignment with IFMIS & GTMI	Fiscal & Implementation Risk
CADENA Act (Senate and House Bills)	Transparency and open-data platform (tech-neutral potential)	Public disclosure of PFM data	High – complements IFMIS as a reporting layer; aligned with DCEI/PSDI principles on transparency and data interoperability	Moderate – manageable if layered on IFMIS; risk arises if parallel reporting systems are created

Bill	Policy Approach	Scope of Reform	Alignment with IFMIS & GTMI	Fiscal & Implementation Risk
SB 433: Digital Assets Act	Financial regulation and market oversight	Digital assets, fintech ecosystem	Moderate – supports GovTech ecosystem (GTEI)	Low – does not disrupt PFM systems
SBN 1330/1463: Blockchain the Budget Bill	Senate version of full migration	Entire PFM system	Very Low – contradicts IFMIS evidence	Very High – same risks as HB 5041
HB 4075: Blockchain for Government Efficiency Act	Technology-prescriptive (framework for use of blockchain)	Cross-government administrative and service delivery processes	Mixed – lacks sequencing, weak link to IFMIS	Moderate–High – risk of fragmentation, siloed use of prescribed tech
HB 4380 / 4489 / 4853 / 4935, 5943, 6909: National Budget Blockchain Acts	Technology-prescriptive (blockchain mandate in the GAA)	Budget preparation, execution, and reporting using blockchain	Low – conflicts with IFMIS-first sequencing; introduces technology before fixing core PFM processes	High – duplication, lock-in, integration costs, provision of P500M without source
HB 7296: Blockchain and Artificial Intelligence for National Budget Transparency and Accountability	Technology-prescriptive (blockchain and AI), with penalty and prohibited acts	Digitize end-to-end budget transactions (planning → disbursement)	Moderate – conflicts with IFMIS-first sequencing, a full-stack digital oversight + execution layer that partially overlaps with core IFMIS functions. Improves visibility but adds complexity and weakens control hierarchy	High –upfront and maintenance cost with uncertain ROI, unproven at this scale
HB 4611 and 5041: Blockchain and the Government Budget	System substitution (blockchain as core financial management system)	All phases of the budget process	Low – attempts to replace core IFMIS functions; inconsistent with global practices	High – major fiscal and technical uncertainty, and major transition risk

Source: Author’s compilation based on Bills uploaded in senate.gov.ph and congress.gov.ph

Introducing blockchain through legislation at this stage risks layering additional costs onto an already resource-intensive and incomplete digital architecture. More importantly, such costs are not one-off expenditures. Similar to other legacy systems, blockchain requires ongoing maintenance, upgrades, cybersecurity safeguards, and interoperability adjustments—thereby increasing the long-term fiscal burden of digital PFM reforms. Several bills require an annual appropriation of P500.0 million without justification as to why and how the said amount was identified. As shown in *Table 3* and *4*, ICT expenditures in the Philippines have increased substantially, reaching nearly P200 billion between 2022 and 2025, with continued growth projected in 2026. These investments are already concentrated in foundational components such as hardware infrastructure, software subscriptions, and connectivity services—elements necessary to support core systems like IFMIS and BTMS.

Comparative assessment shows that policy viability is highest for measures that are technology-neutral and system-compatible, such as the CADENA Act, which focuses on improving transparency through enhanced data disclosure. These approaches align with the Philippines’ identified gaps under the GovTech Maturity Index (GTMI), particularly in citizen engagement and service delivery, and can be effectively implemented if anchored on an established IFMIS.

In contrast, a substantial number of proposals adopt a technology-prescriptive approach, mandating blockchain as a foundational system for PFM processes. These proposals need to be harmonized with both international experience and domestic system readiness. Evidence from IFMIS reforms across Africa, ASEAN, and advanced digital governments consistently demonstrate that core financial management systems must be established and integrated before introducing advanced technologies. No country has successfully implemented blockchain as a full PFM backbone; instead, it is used selectively as a verification or integrity layer. These proposals and the accompanying investments, without clear evidence of improved outcomes, may undermine fiscal sustainability and divert resources from more critical reforms, including system integration and institutional capacity building.

CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The Philippines' push toward digital transformation in PFM reflects a strong commitment to transparency and efficiency, yet the evidence is clear: technology cannot substitute for institutional and systems readiness. The country's core constraint lies not in the absence of advanced tools but in the incomplete integration of IFMIS/BTMS and persistent gaps in governance, interoperability, and capacity, as reflected in GTMI performance and budget execution outcomes. International experience shows that successful reforms are initially sequenced—building integrated core systems before layering advanced technologies. In this light, legislative proposals that prioritize system-wide technological solutions, particularly blockchain, risk misalignment with current system maturity, potentially generating high costs, duplication, and “visibility without reliability”.

Moving forward, effective reform requires a disciplined, system-driven approach anchored on three priorities: i) completing IFMIS integration as the backbone of fiscal management, ii) strengthening governance and institutional capacity, and iii) adopting technology-neutral policies that allow innovations to be deployed selectively and based on proven value. Blockchain, while promising, should be treated as a complementary integrity layer, not a foundational system. Ultimately, the success of digital PFM reform will depend not on how quickly technologies are adopted but on how well they are aligned with institutional capacity, fiscal sustainability, and system coherence—ensuring that innovation delivers measurable improvements rather than reinforcing existing inefficiencies.

In light of the empirical evidence, policy actions must prioritize the alignment of digital innovation with institutional readiness, system integration, and fiscal sustainability. Digital PFM reform should be sequenced, system-driven, and governance-centered, ensuring that technological adoption strengthens—rather than outpaces—the foundations of PFM. The following policy imperatives outline a pragmatic pathway for advancing digitalization in the national budget process and financial reforms:

- ❑ **Adopt Technology-Neutral and Outcome-Based Legislation.** In coming up with a substitute/consolidated House Bill version, legislation should focus on functional outcomes—such as interoperability, real-time reporting, and auditability—rather than mandating specific technologies. This approach preserves flexibility, avoids technological lock-in, and enables adaptive system evolution.
- ❑ **Prioritize IFMIS Integration and Strategic Sequencing.** The completion and full integration of IFMIS/BTMS must be the immediate priority. Advanced technologies should only be introduced once core systems are operational, interoperable, and reliable, consistent with global best practices.
- ❑ **Use Blockchain as a Complementary Integrity Layer.** Legislation is generally not necessary to use blockchain. It should be applied selectively to high-value functions such as document authentication, audit trails, and verification systems. It should not replace core PFM systems but instead enhance specific components where it delivers clear value.
- ❑ **Strengthen Institutional Capacity and Governance Systems.** Reforms must invest in human capital, data governance, audit mechanisms, and inter-agency coordination. Digital tools are only effective when supported by strong institutions, clear accountability frameworks, and enforceable standards.
- ❑ **Develop a Unified, Modular, and Interoperable Digital Architecture.** Adopt a whole-of-government digital architecture anchored on a modular IFMIS design. This enables phased implementation, reduces risk, and ensures that systems evolve toward a single, integrated source of fiscal truth. Legislative initiatives such as the Budget Modernization Act and CADENA Act should be aligned with this architecture and supported by a national digital transformation roadmap to improve GovTech maturity.

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ANNEX I

IFMIS EXPERIENCE IN SELECT ASEAN COUNTRIES

Country	Project / IFMIS Platform	Key Technical Feature	Success / Limitation Factors
Indonesia	SPAN (State Treasury and Budget System)	Integrated IFMIS linking budgeting, treasury, and cash management with centralized database	Success: Strong treasury integration, improved cash management, real-time fiscal reporting Limitation: Initial implementation complexity, capacity gaps at subnational level
Vietnam	TABMIS (Treasury and Budget Management Information System)	Oracle-based IFMIS integrating budget execution and treasury operations	Success: Enhanced fiscal discipline and reporting accuracy Limitation: Limited integration with line agencies; focus remains treasury-centric
Malaysia	GFMAS (Government Financial Management Accounting System)	Integrated accounting and financial reporting system aligned with accrual accounting reforms	Success: Improved financial reporting and compliance Limitation: Partial integration with budgeting and procurement systems
Thailand	GFMS (Government Fiscal Management Information System)	Centralized IFMIS linking budget, accounting, and procurement systems	Success: Strong system integration and improved transparency Limitation: High maintenance cost; dependence on legacy architecture
Philippines	GIFMIS / BTMS (COTS + modular approach)	Modular system linking budget execution and treasury (BTMS) with planned IFMIS integration	Success: Progress in standardization (UACS), improved reporting Limitations: Fragmented systems, incomplete rollout, interoperability challenges

Source: Adapted from Dener et al. (2011); Hashim (2014); World Bank (IEG, 2014); World Bank country reports on Indonesia SPAN and Vietnam TABMIS; and related IFMIS case studies.

ANNEX II

IFMIS EXPERIENCE IN SELECT AFRICAN COUNTRIES

Country	Project / IFMIS Platform	Key Technical Feature	Success / Limitation Factors
Tanzania	IFMIS (Epicor-based system)	Commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) system integrating budgeting, accounting, and reporting	Success: Improved expenditure control and reporting Limitations: Capacity constraints, reliance on external vendors, resistance to system adoption
Ghana	GIFMIS (Oracle-based)	Integrated financial management system covering budget execution, accounting, and treasury operations	Success: Enhanced fiscal reporting and transparency Limitations: Implementation delays, coordination issues, partial rollout across agencies
Kenya	IFMIS (Oracle platform)	End-to-end financial management system linking procurement, budgeting, and payments	Success: Improved procurement transparency Limitations: Implementation delays, coordination issues, partial rollout across agencies

Source: Adopted from Jared et al. (2017); Dener et al. (2011); World Bank IFMIS case studies.

ANNEX III

SELECT INTERNATIONAL AND DOMESTIC BLOCKCHAIN EXPERIENCE

Country	Project / Platform	Type of Blockchain	Key Technical Feature	Success / Limitation Factor
Estonia	KSI Blockchain (Guardtime KSI)	Permissioned	Hash-based Keyless Signature Infrastructure enabling verification of data integrity without exposing content or relying on central trust	Success: High data integrity and cybersecurity resilience; serves as an integrity layer for e-government systems
Georgia	Digital Land Registry (Bitfury / Exonum anchored to Bitcoin)	Hybrid (Public anchoring + private system)	Cryptographic hashing of land records anchored to public blockchain for timestamping and verification	Success: Increased transparency and trust; reduced processing time (≈10 minutes) Limitation: Core administrative processes remain off-chain
Brazil	BNDES Token (BNDESToken on Ethereum / Hyperledger Besu)	Hybrid / Permissioned	Tokenization of public funds with programmable constraints (smart contracts for conditional spending)	Success: Programmatic transparency and reduced fund diversion Limitation: Limited to specific programs, not full PFM system
Philippines (DOST-ASTI)	Verifiable Credentials (SIERRA / DataProtect)	Permissioned	Decentralized identity (DID) and verifiable credentials enabling cryptographic authentication of certificates	Success: Secure, tamper-proof credential verification Limitation: Application limited to identity and certification use cases
Philippines (PSHS)	Pisay-DigiCert (via Twala platform)	Hybrid (Public blockchain anchoring)	Hashing and anchoring of academic records to public blockchain for instant verification	Success: Academic document integrity and lifetime verifiability Limitation: Narrow scope (education records only)
Philippines (DBM)	Action Document Releasing System (ADRS) – Lumen / Polygon	Hybrid (Public blockchain anchoring)	Tokenization of SAROs and NCAs with QR-based verification on blockchain	Success: Improved inter-agency trust and faster verification Limitation: Functions as document authentication layer, not full budget execution system

Source: Author's compilation based on e-Estonia (2023); OECD (2019); Inter-American Development Bank (2021); DOST-ASTI (2023); Philippine Science High School System (2024); Department of Budget and Management (2025).

Congressional Policy and Budget Research Department
3/F Main Building, House of Representatives
Batasan Hills, Quezon City, Metro Manila, Philippines
Tel. No. (DL) 8-931-60-32 (Fax) 8-931-65-19
Website: cpbrd.congress.gov.ph